

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D7.3 Data management and RRI

WP7-Project Management

Version: 1.00

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Executive Summary

CALIPER project aims at implementing Gender Equality Plans in seven (7) Research Performing and two (2) Research Funding organisations. It engages stakeholders both internal and external from the regional/national research and innovation ecosystems with the aim of creating a dialogue on gender & diversity for excellent research, innovation and growth, identifying the gaps and transferring the gained knowledge beyond academia. For this purpose and according to the GEAR toolkit¹, the project will follow five (5) main phases to achieve its end (analysis, planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, sustainability). During the different phases, sex-disaggregated data is collected; procedures, processes and practices are critically assessed with a view to detecting gender inequalities and gender bias while the process and the progress are regularly followed up on and assessed. Findings from the monitoring exercises allow adjustment and improvement measures and activities, so that the results can be optimised (EIGE, GEAR Toolkit). Thus, the project relation with the data collection and process is essential to its objectives and planned activities.

This deliverable represents the first iteration of an ongoing Data management and RRI plan for the CALIPER project. As a dynamic document, it will be updated during the project to reflect the needs of the various partners and the activities undertaken but also and most importantly, in response to any sensitivities or practical constraints which may arise as a result of those activities.

With regards to the Responsible Research and Innovation aspect of the present document, the current project has been designed on its principles² as a cross-cutting issue promoting institutional change, engaging various stakeholders and design an inclusive and sustainable research and innovation environment for the involved RPOs/RFOs and their innovation ecosystems based on the Quadruple helix approach.

The present deliverable corresponds to WP7 Project Management as part of T7.5 Data management plan and ethics and foresees the delivery of the first and single edition of the DMP at month 5. Any additional adjustments after month 5 will be reported in the official technical reports requested by the European Commission (M18, M33, M48).

The deliverable describes i) the set of principles to guide the data collection and preservation including detailed information for the data management lifecycle for all the data sets that will be collected, processed or generated by the project; ii) the methodology and standards of how the data will be shared and/or made accessible and how it will be preserved during and after the lifetime of the project; iii) the responsible research and innovation approach of the project.

¹ Gender equality in academia and research, GEAR tool, European Institute for Gender Equality, 2016 <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/action-toolbox>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

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1 Introduction

This Data management and RRI plan defines the knowledge management strategy of the project, specifying how to facilitate access, re-use and preservation of research data and how scientific publications and produced knowledge will be made publicly available. The present deliverable acts as a living document that presents the consortium's plan for handling the research data during and after the end of the project, the type of data that will be collected, processed and/or generated, the methodology and standards that will be applied. It will also provide a detailed plan on the project data lifecycle, privacy and the project policies for data collection, storage, access, sharing, protection, retention and destruction. All consortium members will refer to this document if any questions regarding data policies and practices.

After consultation with the consortium, three main data usage scenarios are envisaged during the lifecycle of the CALIPER project:

- I. Existing data sourced/procured by the CALIPER consortium during the project's lifetime, especially during the internal assessment and analysis phase of the involved institutions.
- II. Existing data already in possession of the CALIPER consortium to the project's initiation (e.g. publicly available data)
- III. Original data produced by the CALIPER consortium and/or individual members of it (e.g. during the engagement activities, the research and the dissemination activities);

In addition, the datasets handled within the three above scenarios can belong to either of these three categories:

- Confidential data
- Anonymised and Public data
- Non anonymised data (the residual category).

For completeness of information, the reader is advised to refer to the following deliverables:

- D8.3 POPD – H – Requirement No. 3 (submitted to the EC services)
- D8.1 H – Requirement No.1 (when available in M9)
- D8.2 POPD – Requirement No.2 (when available in M9)

1.1 Structure of the deliverable

This document is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the scope of the deliverable and the key scenarios of data usage during and after the lifetime of the project.
- **Chapter 2** presents a brief overview of the legal framework, including the EU regulation on personal data protection (GDPR), the H2020 provisions for open access to research data, the specific provisions of the CALIPER Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.
- **Chapter 3** as the core section of this deliverable presents the overall plan of data management and responsible research and innovation.
- **Chapter 4** summarises the document and presents its conclusions.
- **Annex** contains useful key reference documents and policies.

1.2 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

2 Legal framework

This chapter provides with a brief overview the key normative references of this Data Management Plan. The CALIPER project maintains the required protection of personal data and full compliance to all the Data Regulations in force in national and European legislation about the protection of personal data and has established all the technical means in their reach to avoid the loss, misuse, alteration, access to unauthorised persons and theft of the data provided to this entity, notwithstanding that security measures on the Internet are not impregnable.

The next sub-chapters respectively present:

- The General Data Protection Regulation
- The terms of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) the CALIPER consortium has adhered to;
- The provisions of the Grant and the Consortium Agreements;

2.1 The EU Personal Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Regulation (EU) 2016/679³ sets out the new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) framework in the EU, notably concerning the processing of personal data belonging to EU citizens by individuals, companies or public sector/non-government organisations, irrespective of their localization. This regulation has replaced, and it builds on the principles of the previous Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC. Being a regulation, not a directive, GDPR does not require Member States to pass any enabling legislation and is directly binding and applicable. Key principles under GDPR are ensuring **Lawfulness**, **FAIRNESS** and **transparency** of data processing while consent is a main pillar ensuring fairness of data processing.

2.2 Open Access in Horizon 2020

As indicated in the Guidelines on Data Management in H2020, research data and results should be made FAIR⁴ i.e. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable. While reiterating that the CALIPER project is not a research project, the project and its partners do intend to share and publicise information as widely as possible.

2.2.1 Dissemination materials

Project outcomes and results will become publicly available via the project website, which will include brochures, project deliverables, press releases and newsletters in a dedicated webpage. In addition, information relating to the gender training and capacity-building activities will be linked directly with the website. Further, partners will maintain their own social network (SNS) presence, while the project has established its own social media channels. All shareable, open access material will be available and disseminated to the right stakeholders. More information related to the dissemination and communication plan of the CALIPER project is available through D6.1: Dissemination Strategy (M3).

Namely the following online and offline channels will be used:

³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

⁴ European Commission. (2016). Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020. Retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

- Press Releases
- Newsletters
- Videos
- Project Website
- Social Media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) and partners' channels

2.2.1.1 *Scientific Publications*

Scientific publications are foreseen to be produced during the project cycle. These publications will be accessible to inform and engage the academic community about the projects' procedures, methodologies, and outcomes. Publications through local and international scientific journals will not only target researchers but also the broader public. Two types of scientific publications are foreseen:

Green open access journals: Journals are increasingly allowing authors to self-archive the final peer-reviewed manuscript in repositories (Green open access). Before taking any decisions of where to submit a manuscript, all involved CALIPER researchers will be required to ensure the green open access policy of the journal complies with the requirements posed on H2020 open data access projects: authors must be allowed to self-archive the final peer-reviewed article at the latest 12 months after publication.

Gold open access journals: without author processing fees, or with author processing fees when it is budget wise foreseen.

Another type of publications is also foreseen which aims at the general public; **white papers** and **policy recommendations** which will be publicly available and communicated with the respective target groups.

2.3 Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement provisions

The key GA and CA provisions, worth mentioning in relation to the data management policies, have been already introduced from the project proposal and they are reproduced in the following sections.

The corresponding articles of the GA related to data management policies and procedures are the following:

- 24.1 Agreement on background
- 25.3 Access rights for other beneficiaries, for exploiting their own results
- 26.1 Ownership by the beneficiary that generates the results
- 26.2 Joint ownership by several beneficiaries
- 29.1 Obligation to disseminate results
- 29.2 Open access to scientific publications
- 29.3 Open access to research data
- 39.2 Processing of personal data by the beneficiaries.

The corresponding section of the CA related to data management policies and procedures is the following:

- 9 Section: Access Rights.

3 CALIPER Data Management and RRI Plan

3.1 Data summary

During the CALIPER project, the following data sets have been identified and they are summarised in the following table per Work Package involved. The following type of data will be collected during the different project activities:

Work Package	Type of data
WP1 Analysis of the external and internal conditions for GEPs development and acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publicly available data mined from sources such as reports, books, chapters, articles, blogs, etc. (e.g. good practices) GEPs Working Groups database (only name and affiliation) Contacts of target groups for the internal and external assessment survey, focus groups & interviews; Survey/interview/focus groups results Registration forms and exit questionnaires Training materials, didactic/training exercises Database of national trainers
WP2 Design and development of customised GEPs (CALIPER GEPs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dialogues with external stakeholders at the R&I Hubs (qualitative data)
WP3 Implementation of GEPs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bilateral meetings minutes for tracking the progress of the GEPs implementation Peer learning results from the implementation of GEPs
WP4 Monitoring and evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative and quantitative data will be gathered for the evaluation and monitoring of GEPs
WP5 Engagement, change management and sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contacts of persons in RFOs/RPOs who influence internal changes at management level Contacts of target groups of the innovation ecosystem Internal workshop with GEPs Working Groups Results Publicly available data for identifying the local framework conditions Training sessions registration form (name, surname, email address, job position, interests, learning objectives, etc.) Webinars' videos and recording
WP6 Dissemination and Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publicly available data mined from sources such as reports, books, chapters, articles, blogs, etc. Analytics results from social media channels and the project website Personal data of stakeholders and policy makers Photos/videos shot during public events and project's workshops

WP7 Project Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consortium contact list Advisory Board contact list Any other communication lists and information
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Table 1. Data summary per Work Package

3.2 Data collection and analysis

The project will conduct interviews, surveys, workshops and engagement and dissemination activities which involve volunteers. In the context of these activities CALIPER will collect information regarding the expertise of the participants, in the development of such programmes and regarding their background and interest in participating in the trainings.

The CALIPER project partners will collect primary data and rely on the use of secondary data in their work. To support the delivery of the CALIPER's objectives to the highest quality standard, some research-based activities will be undertaken, and new qualitative and quantitative data will be collected. This means that individuals will be recruited to participate in and provide data in the research-based activities of the project. The collection of new data particularly applies to the evaluation of the internal and external situation of the involved RPOs/RFOs and the work to be performed as part of WP1, WP2 and WP4.

The project partners will recruit adult participants from the realm of business, higher education and research (quadruplex model) in the partner countries in activities some of which involve collection of personal data. The research-related activities planned include individual face-to-face interviews, questionnaire studies, workshops, and online surveys (web surveys). Some participant observation may also be done under WP5. If required under national legislation or practice, copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans will be obtained and kept on file and will be reported in D8.1.

While the focus of the project is not on collecting any personal sensitive data, the nature of the project itself may involve handling potentially sensitive data. The personal data to be collected as part of the research-related activities include names, e-mail addresses, age, gender, position, institution.. It is not planned that sensitive personal data will be collected (although it cannot be excluded that interview partners disclose sensitive information concerning themselves and their work in the course of open face-to-face interviews – it is though considered unlikely).

3.2.1 Informed consent procedures

For all the abovementioned data collection activities informed consent procedures have been developed and they are available on D8.3 POPD – H – Requirement No. 3.

The informed consent materials include an information sheet (Annex I) and an informed consent form (Annex II). These are in language and terms understandable to the participants. The general rights that will form the informed consent procedure comprise the following:

- To know the purpose of the research-related activity and the data collection;
- To know that participation is voluntary;
- To know the degree of risk and burden involved in participation;
- To know who will benefit from participation;
- To know the procedures that will be implemented in the case of incidental findings or findings outside of the scope of the current project;
- To know how their data will be collected, protected during the project and either destroyed or reused at the end of the project;
- To withdraw themselves and their data from the project at any time;
- To know of any potential commercial exploitation of the data.

3.3 Data processing, preservation and storage

ViLabs as the project coordinator is responsible for the internal project environment and oversees the overall project activities. The internal communication is best described at D7.1 Project Management Handbook.

The consortium discusses the possibility to share data, where appropriate, and not otherwise restricted by existing partner agreements, via appropriate repositories, such as the EU supported project zenodo.org (CALIPER Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/caliper-project/?page=1&size=20>), with a general restriction that any such data should be used for non-commercial, preferably research purposes.

The data processing, preservation and storage plan includes:

- **Teamwork:** CALIPER has set up that [Teamwork](#) to use for the project management at internal level. It is managed by the Coordinator (VIL) and offers a Collaborative Working Environment equipped by useful tools and functionalities to support collaboration within the consortium in all phases of the project. The tool allows project progress monitoring, by being constantly informed about the users' activities. All partners involved in the project have access to the platform. The access to the platform is controlled by username and password of personal user account, which is assigned by the platform administrator (VIL). All project participants are granted access to the shared workspace. Each project partner is responsible to notify VIL of changes of project participants in their organization, in order to allow VIL to update the lists of users involved in the various work packages. Any member may also delete the account at any time. Teamwork is a project management tool compliant with all the abovementioned legal frameworks and GDPR compliant. More information can be found, [here](#).
- **Mailing lists** represent the major communication tools used in the CALIPER Project. All mailing lists are closed lists: only members registered for a particular list may send messages to the list and receive as well. To avoid unnecessary emails, each person posting to any of the email lists should ensure that the content of the message is appropriate for the recipients of the list selected. Any member may unsubscribe from any mailing list, any time.
- The [GoToMeeting Tool](#) is used to organize short remote meetings between partners. Remote meetings are held every month. Additional online meetings can be arranged depending on particular needs of the project. The online meetings are recorded, when all participants agree. The minutes are prepared in the format of the Word Document and uploaded at the Project Management Tool accessible for the consortium members only.
- **Project website**, where all the public deliverables are uploaded. It is secure as the HTTPS protocol is installed. Our first concern is the protection of our users. HTTPS protects the privacy and security of our users, by encrypting the communication between the browser that the user is using and the server which hosts the website. This prevents the intruders from being able to passively listen to the communications between the website and the user. This encryption also protects the integrity of our website.

Responsibility for data collection and storage is held by Ms. Vasiliki Moutzi. Responsibility for quality, security and data sharing as well as policy compliance is held by Ms. Vasiliki Moutzi. More information about the responsibilities and the data controllers per each consortium member will be found on D8.2 upon its completion on M9.

Data owners retain the right to be forgotten via communicating to CALIPER's established communication channels info@caliper-project.eu or to the Project Coordinator (mov@vilabs.eu). Enquiries concerns or complaints will be attended within five (5) working days.

3.4 Responsible Research and Innovation guiding principles

According to the EU funded project RRI Tools⁵ and the Horizon 2020 framework programme, Responsible Research and Innovation is a cross-cutting topic as a key action of the 'Science with and for Society' objective. In order to design and implement an RRI compliant project one should take into consideration the RRI guiding principles as depicted in the following figure of the RRI Tools project presentation:

⁵ RRI Tools project (This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no. 612393.) RRI Toolkit. Retrieved from: <https://www.rri-tools.eu/search-engine#keywords=@filterOption=40105@order=@page=1>

What do you do when you do RRI?

Figure 1. RRI Tools project presentation – RRI elements

Those thematic elements of RRI include the considerations for public engagement, open access, gender, ethics and science education via the promotion of institutional change. All the abovementioned are key elements and aspects of the CALIPER project.

Ensure R&I addresses societal challenges: CALIPER aims at promoting structural change in nine research institutions across Europe influencing their innovation ecosystem in positive actions towards gender equality. Gender equality is a crosscutting issue in Horizon 2020 as part of the strategic approach of the European Commission's in the field of research and innovation⁶. The inclusion of the gender dimension at all stages of research and innovations has an enormous potential to enrich results by making them relevant to women as well as men and CALIPER aims at this direction with the development and implementation of the Gender Equality Plans and the influence for change to the innovation environment of its institutions and therefore addressing the societal challenges.

Open R&I to all actors and at all levels: The co-creation of Gender Equality Plans and actions includes public engagement via awareness raising activities, workshops, trainings, surveys, etc. which will bring together multidisciplinary teams to boost creativity and maximize the impact of the project and the research and innovation actions of the involved parties. Multidisciplinary and inclusive teams will be fostered through the development and implementation of the GEPs. The project results will be widely disseminated during and after the lifetime of the project providing open access to all the interested stakeholders and institutions willing to replicate the CALIPER methodology.

Align R&I with societal values, needs and expectations: Complementary to the abovementioned, the Gender Equality Plans will include actions addressing the expectations and the needs of the involved stakeholders and interested parties. The gender dimension will be considered as one of the key aspects of activities towards its integration to gender in teaching and gender pedagogy and the considerations of gender for research and innovation in both the involved RPOs/RFOs and their innovation ecosystems.

⁶ European Commission (2017). Interim Evaluation: Gender equality as a crosscutting issue in Horizon 2020. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_gender_equality/interim_evaluation_gender_long_final.pdf

3.5 Ethical treatment

The main ethical considerations of the CALIPER project and its data are related to privacy. The CALIPER consortium is aware of potential ethical, fundamental rights, privacy and data protection implications that may be identified in the course of the project and the consortium is fully committed to adhere to and promote the highest ethical, fundamental rights and legal standards, as recognized at the European Union and International level, in the project's activities and outcomes. Sensitive information might be revealed about gender discriminatory practices and behaviors at the involved institutions and acknowledges that in case of leakage of such information there might be negative consequences to an employee's position within the organisation. Therefore, keeping employees on the safe side is a priority and all collected personal data will be anonymized and kept confidential and encrypted. The CALIPER consortium will ensure that the project's research ethics comply with relevant national and EU legislation, regardless of the country in which the research is carried out.

The following deliverables are laying out the Ethical Aspects in more detail:

- **D8.1 H – Requirement No.1 (M9):** Any requirements under national legislation or practice, copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans must be obtained and kept on file.
- **D8.2 POPD – Requirement No.2 (M9):** The host institution must confirm that it has appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research. For host institutions not required to appoint a DPO under the GDPR a detailed data protection policy for the project must be kept on file. Detailed information on the procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction, and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation must be kept on file. - In case personal data are transferred from the EU to a non-EU country or international organisation, confirmation that such transfers are in accordance with Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679, must be submitted as a deliverable. - In case personal data are transferred from a non-EU country to the EU (or another third state), confirmation that such transfers comply with the laws of the country in which the data was collected must be submitted as a deliverable.
- **D8.3 POPD – H – Requirement No. 3 (M2):** Detailed information on the informed consent procedures in regard to data processing must be kept on file. Templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) on data processing must be kept on file.

3.5.1 Responsibilities

Each WP leader in collaboration with each Task leader involved in collection, handling and processing of personal data is responsible for ensuring that the anonymity of interview partners is preserved. It is also the WP leaders' responsibility to ensure that all their task leaders in their respective activities of collecting, handling and processing data follow relevant national and/or European legislation. Each partner is furthermore responsible for following their national legislation concerning protection of personal data and involvement of humans in social scientific research.

4 Conclusions

This document represents the fundamental deliverable concerning the CALIPER Data Management Plan (DMP) in fulfilment of the requirements of WP7 and WP8 of the project's work plan. It represents the first iteration of an ongoing Data management and RRI plan for the CALIPER project. As a dynamic document, it will be updated during the project to reflect the needs of the various partners and the activities undertaken but also and most importantly, in response to any sensitivities or practical constraints which may arise as a result of the implementation of planned project activities.

Annex I: References

Ethics and data protection (European Commission, 14 November 2018, here: Ethics and data protection). Retrieved from:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-data-protection_en.pdf

European Commission. (2016). Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020. Retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

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RRI Tools project (This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no. 612393.) RRI Toolkit. Retrieved from: <https://www.rri-tools.eu/search-engine#keywords=@filterOption=40105@order=@page=1>

